

Possible Psychopharmacological Agents, Part XI* : Synthesis and CNS Activity of Some Fluorine Containing Indole Derivatives

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2-(4'-Fluorophenyl)indole undergoes Mannich reaction with 1-arylpiperazines and formaldehyde (40%) to give the corresponding 3-(1-arylpiperazinomethyl)-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indoles. 3-Chloroacetyl-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indole produces 3-(1-arylpiperazinoacetyl)-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indoles by the reaction of the corresponding 1-arylpiperazines. All the compounds have been characterized by IR, PMR and ^{19}F NMR spectral studies. Some compounds have been screened for CNS activity on different parameters.

THE indole derivatives are well known for their biological activities¹⁻⁴. 3-[4(4'-Fluorophenyl)-1-piperazinomethyl]indole has shown good analgesic and antiinflammatory activities^{5,6}. The introduction of fluorine or CF_3 group into an organic molecule increases its solubility in lipid material and fat deposits in the body⁷. 3-Dialkylaminoacetylindole derivatives have been reported to possess analgesic activity⁸.

In view of this, we have now undertaken the synthesis of fluorine containing 3-(1-arylpiperazinomethyl)-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indoles(IIa-f) by the Mannich reaction⁹ of corresponding indoles(Ia-b) with arylpiperazines and formaldehyde (40%) in dioxane at 0° and 3-(1-arylpiperazinoacetyl)-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indoles(IVa-b) by the action of 1-arylpiperazines on 3-chloroacetyl-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indole(III)^{11,12} as CNS agents [Scheme I].

X = 5-F, H

Ar = C₆H₅, C₆H₄, F-p, C₆H₄CF₃-m, C₆H₄Cl-p

SCHEME-I

Experimental

Melting points of all the compounds are uncorrected. IR spectra have been recorded on Perkin-Elmer (model-557) in nujol mull. PMR(60 MHz)

and ^{19}F NMR(56.4 MHz) spectra have been recorded on Perkin-Elmer (model RB-12). TMS was taken as internal standard for PMR spectra, and TFA was taken as external standard for ^{19}F NMR spectra.

2-(4'-Fluorophenyl)indole(Ia), 5-fluoro-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indole(Ib) and 3-chloroacetyl-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indole have been prepared by the method of Joshi *et al*^{11,12}.

3-(1-Arylpiperazinomethyl)-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indoles(IIa-f)

A solution of 5-F/H-2-(4'fluorophenyl)indole (0.01 mole) in dioxane (20 ml) was added to a cooled solution of formaldehyde (0.01 mole, 40%) and appropriate phenylpiperazine (0.012 mole) in acetic acid (glacial; 5 ml) during 30 min. The whole reaction mixture was further stirred for 3-4 hrs at 0-5° and then diluted with water. It was filtered and the filtrate on basification afforded the desired compounds. The compounds were purified by recrystallization from ethanol and gave single spots on TLC (Table 1).

3-(1-Arylpiperazinoacetyl)-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indoles(IVa-b) :

3-Chloroacetyl-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indole(III, 0.01 mole) was refluxed with appropriate 1-arylpiperazine (0.015 mole) in ethanol for 3 to 4 hrs. The reaction mixture, on cooling, gave the desired compound which was filtered and recrystallized with ethanol. The compounds gave single spots in TLC.

The characteristic and analytic data are recorded in Table 1.

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TABLE I—CHARACTERISTIC AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF FLUORINE CONTAINING INDOLE DERIVATIVES

Sl. No.	X	Y	Substituent in Ar	Yield (% of theory)	M.P. °C	Molecular Formula*	% of Nitrogen	
							Calcd.	Found
IIa	H	-CH ₂ -	4-F	62	170	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ F ₂ N ₂	10.42	10.31
IIb	H	-CH ₂ -	4-Cl	59	159	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ ClFN ₂	10.01	9.84
IIc	H	-CH ₂ -	H	61	189	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ FN ₂	10.90	10.70
IId	H	-CH ₂ -	3-CF ₃	58	137	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ F ₃ N ₂	9.27	9.32
IIe	5-F	-CH ₂ -	3-CF ₃	54	143	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ F ₅ N ₂	8.91	8.68
IIf	5-F	-CH ₂ -	4-F	52	128-30	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ F ₃ N ₂	9.97	9.82
IVa	H	-COCH ₂ -	H	58	188-89	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ FN ₂ O	10.17	9.84
IVb	H	-COCH ₂ -	4-Cl	63	177	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ ClFN ₂ O	9.38	9.12

* Satisfactory C and H analyses results were obtained.

IR (Nujol mull) cm⁻¹ ; 3200-3400 (>NH), 1200-1400 (C-F stretching) and 1625-1640 (C=O in compound Nos. IVa and IVb).

PMR(TFA) δppm ; 7.8-8.2 (>NH), 3.9-4.1(-CH₂-N<CH₂-CH₂>N-) and 4.3-4.4(-C(=O)-CH₂-N< in compound Nos. IVa and IVb).

¹⁹F NMR Acetone) ppm ; 39.0-42.0 (Ar-F), 49.0(5-F in compound Nos. IIe and IIf) and -10.7(Ar-CF₃ in compound Nos. IId and IIe).

TABLE 2—GROSS ACTIVITY OF FLUORINE CONTAINING INDOLE DERIVATIVES

Compd. Sl. No.	Dose mg/kg	Gross Behaviour							Acute toxicity		
		SMA	Respiration	Reactivity Sound	Touch	Writhing	Ataxia	Catal-epsy	Convulsions	Mortality	ALD ₅₀ mg/kg
IIa	464	↑	↑	↑	↑	-	-	-	-	0	>1000
	1000	↑	↑	↑	↑	-	-	-	-	0	
	200	↑	↑	↑	↑	-	-	-	-	0	
IIb	464	↑	↑	↑	↑	+	-	-	-	0	>1000
	1000	↑	↑	↑	↑	+	-	-	+	0	
	200	↑	↑	↑	↑	-	-	-	-	0	
IIc	464	↑	↑	↑	↑	+	-	-	-	0	>1000
	1000	↑	↑	↑	↑	+	-	-	-	0	
	200	↑	↑	↑	↑	-	-	-	-	0	
IVa	464	↑	↑	↑	↑	-	-	-	-	0	>1000
	1000	↑	↑	↑	↑	-	-	-	-	0	
	200	↑	↑	↑	↑	-	-	-	-	0	
IVb	464	↑	↑	↑	↑	-	-	-	-	0	>1000
	1000	↑	↑	↑	↑	-	-	-	-	0	
	200	↑	↑	↑	↑	-	-	-	-	0	
IVc	464	↓	↓	↓	↓	-	+	+	+	0	681
	1000	↓ ↓	↓ ↓	↓ ↓	↓ ↓	-	++	+	-	100	
	136.2	↓	↓	↓	↓	-	-	-	-	0	

SMA = Spontaneous motor activity.
 ↓ or ↑ = decrease or increase.
 + or ++ = mild or strong effect.
 - = No effect.

CNS Activity :

Compound Nos. IIa, IIb, IIc, IVa and IVb in Table I and IVc [3-diethylaminoacetyl-2-(4'-fluorophenyl)indole] have been screened for CNS activity on different parameters in mice of either sex weighing between 18-25 gms. All the compounds were administered intraperitoneally (i.p.) as suspension in gum acacia.

1. Acute Toxicity : The compounds were administered to groups of mice in increasing doses¹³. The animals were observed for 24 hrs and the lethality after that time was used for determining the LD₅₀ values. At least 3 dose levels were obtained between levels of 100% mortality and no mortality in each case.

The compounds are not toxic. Approximate LD_{50} is more than 1000 mg/kg in all cases except IVc. ALD_{50} for IVc is 681 mg/kg.

2. *Gross Effects* : The animals were observed for 2 hrs after drug administration for any evidence of CNS stimulation or depression or any autonomic effect by the method of Dhar *et al*¹⁴. This involved noting the effects on (i) spontaneous motor activity (ii) certain reflexes eg. righting, corneal and pinnal (iii) muscle tone (reduced and catalepsy) (iv) ataxia and writhing (v) eyes (pupils and ptosis) (vi) respiration, and (vii) observing them for the occurrence of tremors, convulsions, straub's tail, piloerection. Each effect was graded as mild(+) or strong(++).

SMA, respiration and reactivity increases in compound Nos. IIa, IIb, IIc, IVa and IVb, but decreases in IVc. Therefore, all compounds except IVc are stimulant. The results have been recorded in Table 2.

3. *Analgesic Activity* : This was tested by tail pinch method¹⁵. The compounds have been found devoid of analgesic activity.

4. *Anticonvulsant Activity* : This was tested by Supra Maximal Electroshock Seizure pattern¹⁶. The mice were fixed with electrode clamps on the ears. An electric current (48 mA, 0.2 sec.) was passed with a Techno Convulsometer and it induced tonic extension of hind limbs in 100% of untreated controls. The test compounds were administered i.p. to animals and half an hour later electroshock was given. The effective compounds protected electric shock.

Compound No. IVc has shown 20% anti-convulsant activity.

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